

The impact of self-efficacy and training and support on perceived ease of use on enrollment management system adoption: A technological acceptance model-based analysis

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Abstract

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Enrollment management systems (EMS) have become essential tools for higher education institutions that want to succeed in a competitive and changing environment. An enrollment management system (EMS) is a software solution developed to assist institutions in managing their student enrollment system. The study seeks to evaluate the effects of self-efficacy, training and support, and behavioral intention to use the enrollment management system at San Beda University. The sample data were acquired from 90 San Beda University personnel who used the enrollment management system (EMS) using a structured questionnaire survey with a 5-Likert scale. The samples were then processed using a structural equation model (SEM) and path analysis. The study shows that Self-Efficacy has influenced Behavioral Intention (t-statistic=4.483, p-value<0.000), Perceived Ease of Use (t-statistics=2.834, p-value<0.005, Training and Support (t-statistics=2.679, p-value<0.007) which indicates that three hypotheses are supported, while results for Training and Supports revealed its weak impact on Behavioral Intention (t-statistics=0.766, p-value<0.444), Perceived Ease of Use (t-statistics=0.112, p-value<0.499) which indicate that the employees may learn and adapt, eventually using the enrollment management system with less supervision. This means that higher levels of self-efficacy result in greater perceived ease of use, which may favor the adoption and utilization of the enrollment management system. This also suggests that increased self-efficacy can lead to better training and support, ultimately leading to more effective and efficient use of the enrollment management system. This suggests that the enrollment management system is easy to understand and user-friendly. The findings of this study contribute to developing an enrollment management system that is highly usable and provides additional benefits to users. This study will serve as a future reference for administrators, academics, and policymakers in higher education institutions. Higher educational institutions may need to incorporate current study findings into their enrollment process to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of new technology.

Keywords: enrollment management system, perceived ease of use, self-efficacy, training and support, technological acceptance model (TAM)

Introduction

Higher education institutions are increasingly using enrollment management systems (EMS) due to financial challenges, increased student competitiveness, and a desire to optimize resources. Enrollment management systems are more than just enticing more students; they include multidimensional approaches to managing the full student lifecycle, from initial recruitment to retention and graduation. As a result, higher education institutions are constantly looking for innovative and functional technologies to boost production and efficiency while meeting the different needs of students and employees. Enrollment has become challenging due to high wait times and crowding. Technological techniques such as enrollment management systems (EMS) are the most effective solution to address this issue. To address these difficulties, many universities have begun to implement various technologies, including learning management systems (LMS) and enrollment management systems (EMS). Business organizations, including higher education institutions, employ a variety of information systems to record the everyday regular transactions required to

conduct business. Office automation systems support office tasks, while process control systems monitor and control industrial or physical processes. Management information systems (MIS) convert internal data into information that administrators can use to make timely and effective decisions for planning, directing, and controlling their activities (Al- Mamary et al., 2014). The primary functions of information systems are to support business processes, staff decision-making, and competitive strategies (O'Brien & Marakas, 2007). According to Laudon and Laudon (2007), the role of information systems is to assist institutions in achieving operational excellence, improving their operations' efficiency and leading to higher profitability. To increase higher education enrollment, schools must embrace and apply techniques for maintaining consistent communication, streamlining operations, making data-driven decisions, and collaborating seamlessly. An enrollment management system, when properly implemented, allows institutions to improve staff efficiencies and optimize institutional resources while improving the overall student experience, resulting in higher enrollment, revenue, and longevity.

Furthermore, the enrollment management system is a sophisticated system that includes a variety of features aimed at streamlining operations, improving data-driven decision-making, and ultimately increasing staff efficiency. However, successful adoption of these systems requires more than just getting the technology. It involves a thorough grasp of the human aspects that influence user behavior and, ultimately, the system's performance. The problems of implementing an enrollment management system can be divided into three categories: technological, organizational, and human aspects. Adopting a new system frequently disrupts existing workflows and requires employees to master new procedures. Individuals who are content with the status quo or who are afraid of losing control over their work may object. Using the enrollment management system necessitates integrating data from several sources, which can be complicated and time-consuming. Ensuring data accuracy, consistency, and accessibility is critical for making informed decisions. Additionally, the system deployment should be connected with the institution's strategic goals, such as student recruitment, retention, and overall success. Failure to connect the system with institutional priorities can result in inefficiencies and a lack of commitment from key

stakeholders. Implementing and maintaining an enrollment management system necessitates substantial resources, including financial commitment, technical expertise, and devoted personnel. Institutions with limited resources may struggle to successfully deploy and use the system.

Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the adoption of technology in various contexts, including education; nevertheless, the impact of self-efficacy, as well as training and support, on the adoption of enrollment management systems within higher education institutions has received little attention. The majority of research focus primarily on the technology acceptance model (TAM), which stresses perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. However, the TAM fails to capture the intricate interplay of human elements that influence user behavior, including self-efficacy, training, and support. Finally, while there are several studies on technology acceptance in higher education, the most of them focus on general learning technologies, overlooking the special problems and opportunities given by enrollment management systems. This study looks at the importance of self-efficacy, training, and assistance in determining user perceptions of enrollment management system (EMS) ease of use. According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are the most important factors influencing user intention to use and actual use of a technology. This study applies the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) to investigate the impact of self-efficacy, training, and assistance on perceived ease of use, ultimately contributing to a more complete knowledge of enrollment management system (EMS) acceptance.

Statement of the Problem

This study will investigate on the following questions:

1. To what extent do self-efficacy, training, and support influence perceived ease of use on enrollment management systems?
2. What is the relationship between perceived ease of use and adoption of enrollment management systems?
3. How can educational institutions like San Beda University leverage self-efficacy and training and support to facilitate successful enrollment management system (EMS) adoption?

Statement of Objectives

The main objective of this study is to understand how self-efficacy and training and support influence the perceived ease of use of the enrollment management system (EMS), ultimately impacting its adoption rate. More detailed specification objectives are as follows:

1. To determine and measure the relationship between self-efficacy and perceived ease of use in enrollment management system adoption among the employees of San Beda University.
2. To assess the impact of training and support programs on user's perceived ease of use on enrollment management system adoption.
3. To determine how self-efficacy, training, and support interact to influence perceived ease of use and enrollment management system adoption.
4. To develop practical recommendations for HEIs to enhance their enrollment processes through the effective integration of technology based on the findings of the TAM analysis.

Significance of the study

The study has important implications for educational institutions that want to improve enrollment management system (EMS) use. Understanding the relationship between self-efficacy, training, and support on perceived ease of use and eventual adoption enables educational institutions to establish focused methods to improve user acceptability and optimize the benefits of enrollment management (EMS) implementations. The findings will help to deepen our understanding of the elements that influence technology adoption in educational settings and provide useful insights for administrators and technology developers.

Scope and limitations of the study

The primary purpose of this research is to improve our understanding of the factors that influence perceived ease of use in enrollment management system adoption using the TAM framework. The study focuses on San Beda University employees who use the enrollment management system to facilitate enrollment operations. It will examine the relationship between self-efficacy, training, and support and their impact on perceived ease of use, with the ultimate goal of influencing enrollment management system acceptance. The study's weaknesses include its limited geographic scope and sample size.

Literature review

Theoretical background and concept underpinnings

The Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) is used in the study to represent the research phenomenon. The Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) is an information system theory that describes how to persuade consumers to adopt and use new technologies (Davis, 1989). Information systems experts have frequently used it to address the issues that educational institutions have in encouraging the adoption of new information systems (Liu, Dedehayir, and Katzy, 2015). The researcher will use Fred Davis' framework to investigate the relationship of the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) constructs, specifically perceived ease of use on self-efficacy and training and support on enrollment management system adoption, and how it influences the overall experience of San Beda University employees.

Technological Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technological Acceptance Model (Tam) is one of the most essential theories of technology adoption, with two key elements influencing an individual's intention to utilize new technology: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989; Chuttur, 2009). Perceived usefulness is a belief that adopting a specific system will improve personal and professional performance (Davis, 1989; Tyas et al., 2019). Perceived ease of use is a person's belief that using a specific system will require minimal effort (Davis, 1989) and that technology can be easily

comprehended and used (Tyas et al., 2019). Furthermore, the Technological Adoption Model (TAM) is a behavioral theory developed by Fred Davis in 1989 that is commonly used to explain the adoption of information technology along with certain variables that can influence perceptions of technology use. According to Rampen and Sihotang (2021), user acceptance of an information system is defined as the user group's apparent intention to apply the information system. The Technological Adoption Model (TAM) is regarded as capable of providing an understanding of complicated human behavior and expanding the further analysis of the components that influence behavior toward adopting a certain technology (Shaik et al. 2020). Furthermore, the core idea of TAM is that the more employees believe a given technological application will improve their performance and the less effort it takes to utilize, the higher the adoption rate. It will imply that perceived ease of use influences their intention to utilize the technology, leading to actual use.

Finally, this study is based on the TAM Framework because it gives a solid theoretical foundation for understanding individual technology adoption decisions to utilize or reject the new enrollment management system. It assists in identifying the major elements impacting enrollment management system (EMS) adoption, emphasizing the significance of perceived ease of use in determining employee behavior. Finally, this paradigm has been used in earlier works by Shachak et al. (2019), Zheng and Li (2020), Wang (2021), and Tharsarani and Jianguo (2022). Using the TAM, organizations may build strategies to increase technology adoption, improve enrollment processes, and achieve higher efficiency and accuracy in enrollment management.

Figure 1. Technological Acceptance Model (Venkatesh and Davis, 1996)

Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use was described as a person's perception of how much the usage of a specific technology improves performance. This construct was developed using Bandura's concept of outcome judgment, which relates to an individual's expectation of a positive outcome motivating behavior (Bandura, 1982). Perceived usefulness was examined utilizing evidence that confirmed the effect of system performance expectancy on system utilization. Furthermore, perceived ease of use is related to how simple it is to use a technology system and its display. According to Davis's (1986) Technological Acceptance Model (TAM), perceived ease of use is one of the most important variables in user acceptance of new technology. Davis (1986) defined ease of use as the degree to which users assume that utilizing a particular system will require no effort. In other words, the more users believe a system is simple to use, the

more positive their view toward the system. Similarly, if San Beda University staff believe the new enrollment management system is simple, they are likelier to adopt it. A system can be considered quality if it is designed to fulfill user satisfaction through ease of use, which includes not only the ease of learning and using the system but also the ease of executing a job or task (Aryani et al., 2018; Nguyen, 2020; Nguyen, X.T., and Luu, Q., 2020).

Behavioral Intention to Use

According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), behavioral intentions are the agent's perceived probability of carrying out the behavior. This concept was rejected by Warshaw and Davis (1985), who defined behavioral intention as the extent to which a person has made deliberate preparations to conduct or not perform a specific future behavior. In 1991, Ajzen performed additional research on behavioral intention and concluded that it shows how hard people are willing to try and how much work they expect to put in. The Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) has gained popularity, and most studies have demonstrated that its constructs are useful while employing technology. As a result, in the context of information technology systems, namely the acceptance of enrollment systems, behavioral intention refers to the actual usage of the technology. Behavioral intention about perceived ease of use refers to how technology may be used and incorporated into employees' everyday routines, resulting in greater productivity.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to do a task successfully, is essential in the adoption of enrollment management. According to Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, self-efficacy is a human concept influenced by behaviors and social or environmental circumstances. Bandura (1986; p391) similarly proposed that self-efficacy affected performance primarily by boosting a person's effort and persistence. Schunk and DiBenedetto (2021) defined self-efficacy as the perceived ability to learn or do tasks at specific levels. They also highlighted that a significant motivational construct influences choices, effort, persistence, and achievement. This has been confirmed by Stajkovic and Sergent (2019), whose research found that self-efficacy had a critical role in affecting behavior and performance. The study found that higher levels of self-efficacy are connected with better drive, resilience, and achievement. Individuals with strong self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to set challenging goals, persevere in adversity, and eventually achieve more significant results, which is critical for enrollment management system acceptance.

Training and Support

In this study, the researcher highlighted training and assistance, specifically technical help, which is critical in implementing an enrollment management system. Individuals, particularly San Beda University personnel who utilize the enrollment management system, require extensive training and support. Managing enrollment and providing staff with strong experience across institutions necessitates embracing new trends, taking creative risks, and assessing existing systems. Adopting a new enrollment management system can interrupt employees' focus on their current tasks, leading to resistance to the system's implementation. In this circumstance, proper training is required for employees to use the new system efficiently. This includes offering extensive training materials, hands-on practice sessions, and ongoing assistance to ensure employees know the system's capabilities and functionalities (Hosler, 2014). Imran et al. (2020) found that organizational support is essential in improving employee engagement. It was discovered that when employees are supported by their employers, they feel flourishing, thriving, and highly engaged, proving their effectiveness in contributing to attaining goals. Finally, training and assistance are critical for harnessing the power of technology and realizing its full potential, which leads to greater productivity.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual model for a technical acceptability model for the enrollment management system was created to investigate user acceptance. This model includes self-efficacy, training, and support as external variables that will be combined with the Perceived Ease of utilization (PEAU) of the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) to predict the Behavioral Intention (BI) of San Beda University personnel to utilize the enrollment management system.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of the Study. Source: Jarabo, J. (2024)

Six hypotheses were developed based on the proposed conceptual model in this study. The hypotheses are:

H1: There is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and behavioral intention to use an enrollment management system.

H2. A significant relationship exists between self-efficacy and perceived ease of use on enrollment management system adoption.

H3. A significant relationship exists between self-efficacy, training, and support on adoption of enrollment management systems.

H4. Perceived ease of use mediates the relationship between self-efficacy and behavioral intention to use an enrollment management system.

H5. Training and support mediate the relationship between self-efficacy and behavioral Intention to use the enrollment management system.

H6. There is a significant relationship between training and support and behavioral Intention to use an enrollment management system.

H7: There is a significant relationship between training and support and perceived ease of use of the enrollment management system.

Methodology

Research Procedures of Data Collections

This study employs a quantitative approach to assess and analyze San Beda University workers' attitudes regarding implementing an enrollment management system. Creswell (2013) described quantitative research as research that explains phenomena through numerical data collected and evaluated using mathematical methodologies, namely statistical approaches. A systematic survey questionnaire was used to obtain data on the TAM construct of perceived ease of use, which was then supplemented with an external variable of self-efficacy and training and assistance. The questionnaire also included questions regarding San Beda University employees' demographic data, such as age, gender, years of service, and employment status.

To assess the constructs, the researcher employed the 5-Likert Scale (1=Strongly Disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly Agree). The researcher utilized the Likert scale since it is one of the most fundamental and widely used techniques in educational and social sciences research (Joshi et al. (2015), particularly in determining participants' perceptions.

Sampling Design and Research Participants

The researcher used purposive sampling, and 90 San Beda University employees who were directly involved in implementing and using the enrollment management system were chosen. In summary, the sample is rather uneven in terms of age and years of service because most employees who utilize the enrollment management system are young.

Data Analysis and Analytical Tools

The study employs data analysis approaches such as Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) via the SMARTPLS4 program. This method allows the researcher to perform three actions simultaneously: testing and analyzing the validity and reliability of data, testing the relationship between latent variables, and structuring the suitable model and a Structural Model (Hair et al., 2022). The measurement model depicts the influence of the link between constructs and indicators. At the same time, the structural model describes the route relationships between constructs.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics calculated using SMARTPLS4 are shown below to provide a more complete picture of the survey data utilized in this study. The data is analyzed using frequency distributions and valid percentages.

Table 1 shows the demographic breakdown of the 90 useable surveys: 49 (54.50%) were male, 37 (41.10%) were female, and 4 (4.40%) decided not to disclose their gender. Most participants, 45 (50%), were under 20 to 30. Regarding employment status, 85 (94.50%) respondents were regular employees.

Most answers (45.60%) are in the 1-to-10-year range regarding years of service or tenure at the institution, indicating that many regular employees were employed recently. As a result, the sample is uneven in terms of age, employment status, and years of service, as most enrollment management system users are young.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

Measure	Value	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Gender	Male	49	54.45%
	Female	37	41.11%
	Preferred not to say	4	4.44%
Age	20 to 30 years	45	50.00%
	31 to 40 years	32	35.56%
	41 to 50 years	10	11.11%
	51 to 60 years	3	3.33%

Employment Status	Regular	85	94.45%
	Contractual	4	4.44%
Years of Service	Probationary	1	1.11%
	Less than 1 year	5	5.56%
	1 to 10 years	41	45.56%
	11 to 20 years	31	34.44%
	21 to 30 years	10	11.11%
	31 years above	3	3.33%

*This is obtained by using the structured survey questionnaire and measured through the use of 5-Liker

Reliability and Validity Analysis

According to Hair et al. (2017), evaluating a measurement model entail investigating the validity and reliability of the association between latent constructs and their relationships. The measuring model included tests for indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability, and convergent and discriminant validity. The results reveal that the indicator dependability because the majority of the factor loadings were greater than 0.7, except for the five indicators Effic1 (0.717), Train2 (0.283), Train5 (0.557), PEAU (0.541), and PEAU (0.493). These indicators did not match the suggested threshold and influenced the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) of constructs; hence, they were eliminated.

Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the reliability and consistency of the constructs in the proposed model. According to the results in Table 2, all Cronbach Alpha values for the constructs exceeded the acceptable value of >0.60 and composite reliability of >0.70 (Hair et al., 2022). All constructs (self-efficacy=0.914; training and support=0.943; perceived ease of use=0.922; behavior intention=0.946) had Cronbach Alpha values more than 0.60. In the composite reliability test (rho_a), all constructs (self-efficacy=0.914; training and support=1.012; perceived ease of use=0.948; behavioral intention=0.946) had values more than 0.70, considered acceptable. The findings show that all of the constructs in the suggested study model have sufficient reliability.

Table 2. Results of Reliability and Convergent Validity Analysis

Constructs	Cronbach's	Composite Reliability	Alpha (rho_a)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Self-Efficacy		0.914	0.914	0.796
Training and Support		0.943	1.012	0.944
Perceived Ease of Use		0.922	0.948	0.864
Behavioral Intention		0.946	0.956	0.86

*Values were obtained using the SMARTPLS4

The resultant model was used to assess indicator reliability, construct reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. The AVE of the concept must be greater than 0.5 to accept convergent validity, and Table 2 shows that all constructs have an AVE between 0.796 and 0.860, indicating that the latent constructs are convergent. Second, composite reliability is larger than AVE, demonstrating concept convergent validity. Furthermore, convergent validity suggests how well a test evaluates the theoretical construct that served as the foundation for its development. It is considered legitimate or good if the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value exceeds 0.5 (Abdillah, 2016; Hair et al., 2022). According to Table 2, the AVE value for each construct (Self-Efficacy=0.796; Training and Support=0.944; PEAU=0.864; Behavioral Intention=0.860) indicates high construct validity because it is more significant than 0.50.

Table 3. Results of Discriminant Validity – Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (rho a)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Self-Efficacy	0.914	0.914	0.796
Training and Support	0.943	1.012	0.944
Perceived Ease of Use	0.922	0.948	0.864
Behavioral Intention	0.946	0.956	0.86

*Values were obtained using the SMARTPLS4

The HTMT ratio was employed to assess discriminant validity, and its value ranged from 0.078 to 0.565. All values were smaller than 0.90, indicating approval of measurement model discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015). Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015) suggested testing the discriminant validity by calculating the correlations' Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) values. Table 3 shows discriminant validity results using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT). All HTMT values were less than 0.90, indicating that the suggested model is acceptable.

Hypothesis Evaluation

The following are the results of hypothesis testing using PLS-SEM in this study.

Table 4. Results of Structural Modeling Analysis – Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T- Statistics	P-Value	Decision
H1	Effic → BI	0.553	0.123	4.483	0.000	Supported
H2	Effic → PEAU	0.322	0.114	2.834	0.005	Supported
H3	Effic → Train	0.321	0.120	2.679	0.007	Supported
H4	Effic → PEAU → BI	-0.002	0.038	0.042	0.967	Not Supported
H5	Effic → Train → BI	-0.021	0.034	0.624	0.533	Not Supported
H6	Train → BI	-0.066	0.086	0.766	0.444	Not Supported
H7	Train → PEAU	-0.076	0.112	0.112	0.499	Not Supported

*Results are obtained using the SMARTPLS 4 Software. *Effic =Self-Efficacy, PEAU=Perceived Ease of Use, Train=Training and Support, BI=Behavioral Intention

The measurement variables are considered significant if the t-statistics value is larger than 1.96, and the p-value is less than 0.05 at a 5% significance level. The test results (Table 4) show that the variables Self-efficacy (Effic) and Behavioral Intention (BI) (t-stat=4.483, p-value<0.000) and Self-Efficacy (Effic) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEAU) (t-stat=2.834, p-value<0.005) have a positive effect on enrollment management system acceptance, supporting H1 and H2. This finding has been supported by Stajkovic and Sergent (2019), who found that self-efficacy had a critical role in affecting behavior and performance. Self-efficacy (Effic) and Training and Support (t-statistics=2.679, p-value<0.007) positively impact enrollment management system acceptance, supporting hypothesis H3. The enrollment management system's acceptance is weakly influenced by self-efficacy (Effic), perceived ease of use (PEAU), behavioral intention (BI) (t-statistics=0.042, p-value=0.967), training and support (Train), and behavioral intention (BI) (t-statistic=0.624, p-value<0.533). Therefore, H4 and H5 are not supported. Training and Support (Train) and Behavioral Intention (BI) (t-statistics=0.766, p-value<0.444) and Training and

Support (Train) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEAU) (t-statistics=0.112, p-value<0.499) have a weak effect on the acceptance of the enrollment management system. Therefore, H6 and H7 are not supported.

Table 5. Model Fit

	Estimated Model	Interpretation
SRMR	0.060	Highly Fit
NFI	0.749	Moderately Fit

*Values were obtained using the SMARTPLS4

Furthermore, the model's approximate appropriateness was tested using model fit, which required an SRMR value of less than 0.08 and an NFI value greater than 0.90. In this investigation, the SRMR was 0.060, and the NFI was 0.749 (see Table 5), indicating that the model was satisfactory.

Table 6. Collinearity Statistics (VIF) – Inner Model

Relationship	VIF
Self-Efficacy → Behavioral Intention	1.229
Self-Efficacy → Perceived Ease of Use	1.115
Self-Efficacy → Training and Support	1.000
Perceived Ease of Use → Behavioral Intention	1.104
Training and Support → Behavioral Intention	1.121
Training and Support → Perceived Ease of Use	1.115

*Values were obtained using the SMARTPLS4

VIF values were used to verify collinearity before evaluating the structural models. As indicated in Table 6, all VIF values were less than 5, indicating no collinearity. The values of Self-Efficacy - Behavioral Intention (1.229), Self-Efficacy - Perceived Ease of Use (1.115), Self-Efficacy - Training and Support (1.000), Perceived Ease of Use - Behavioral Intention (1.104), Training and Support - Behavioral Intention (1.121), and Training and Support - Perceived Ease of Use (1.115) were all less than 5, indicating that there was no collinearity.

Figure 3. Final Structural Equation Modeling

Conclusion

This study concludes that self-efficacy influences the adoption of San Beda University's enrollment management system. Employees feel they can complete their responsibilities successfully based on their strengths. Stajkovic and Sergent (2019) discovered that the higher the employees' self-efficacy, the more likely they are to adopt the enrollment management system and other new technologies. Employees with high self-efficacy are more confident in their ability to learn and adapt, resulting in increased engagement and likelihood of continuous use. Furthermore, personnel with higher self-efficacy can help the institution save money on training because they can rapidly learn the essentials and utilize the enrollment management system effectively without needing specialist teaching. The data revealed that Training and Support have a weak association with Behavioral Intention, whereas Perceived Ease of Use has a weak mediating effect. This means that the institution's Training and Support system must be improved to convince staff to accept the enrollment management system and recognize the value of embracing new technology. In terms of Perceived Ease of Use, the institution should educate its workers on the features and functionalities of the enrollment management system to familiarize them with the new technology. The better employees understand the enrollment management system's features and functionalities, the more confident they will use the latest technology in their everyday duties.

This study may benefit higher education institutions by focusing on critical elements that can be examined to improve enrollment processes for both personnel and students. For academic purposes, the study might be utilized to conduct additional research on the acceptance aspects of enrollment management systems by examining variables other than those in this study. This will discover new factors that can influence enrollment management system acceptance. For society, it is envisaged that this study will provide public insights into the enrollment management system. This study's limitations are its geographic coverage and small sample size, which can be improved in future research.

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